

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT PRESCHOOLS USING CONTEMPORARY METHODS. REGARDING FOREIGN APPROACHES.

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Annotation : The purpose of this scientific article is to further improve the modern methodology of teaching foreign languages in the process of preschool education, based on foreign methodologies, and to apply them widely in our region. Working through visual aids, posters and books. and Using songs and action games to enhance the classroom environment. The role of gestures and facial expressions in raising the level of education. We will consider the use of such methods when working with children of kindergarten age.

Keywords : preschools , methods, approaches, teaching foreign languages, classroom environment , language abilities , visual aids.

Introduction : As we know that today, increasing the quality of education and improving it is of great importance. and the demand for learning languages is increasing, especially the demand for learning English is very high. Learning a language can be a bit difficult for older people or teenagers, so it is important and more effective to learn a language from an early age, before school. and in this article we will look at language learning with young people, its methods and problems.

Going over books, posters, and visual aids. Primary school pupils in rural locations typically grow up far from an English-speaking environment. As a result, their thinking is typically still abstract, and learning new information is constantly based on emotions. Thus, in order to teach English to students of kindergarten age using simple techniques, English teachers make full use of the materials available to them, flashcards, and other teaching aids. Teachers can teach new terms for color while teaching words like "tomato" and "potato" by demonstrating fruits like tomatoes and

potatoes. Through classroom tools used to arrange educational lessons, children learn how to use them in a foreign language. Teaching foreign languages at preschools using contemporary methods.

Naturally, the way that materials are used in the classroom greatly depends on the teaching style of the instructor. When teaching related words, for instance, you might first show the child the object and urge him to speak it, then have the children pronounce the words before having them repeat the new word while pointing to the images on the cards to help them remember how to say it. Teachers can choose the text's content when teaching words, and to catch students' attention, they can create a picture of them on the board while simultaneously saying the words. As a result, having sketching skills is currently a requirement for teachers in China. This helps pupils gradually consolidate what they have learnt while simultaneously lowering the complexity of teaching. A correct approach to each educational task is required in order for students to sense their progress in the process of learning the English language. Children can only be inspired to learn in this way. The training programs in kindergartens have been enhanced in accordance with the fact that Chinese kindergarten-aged youngsters are now better equipped to absorb new information.

Enhancing the classroom atmosphere using music and interactive games.

Sometimes, a flexible classroom environment is more crucial than any teaching strategy. At the start of the lesson, the teacher led the entire class in singing a song in the classroom. By itself, this will assist them in getting physical activity, boosting their energy levels, and memorizing the song's words more quickly. Importantly, the English environment makes it easy to settle into a positive learning environment. Children have poor self-control, making it challenging for them to focus and maintain their attention during the entire class. Therefore, the teacher should give the students songs they enjoy listening to, poetry or brief sayings to learn the language, or if necessary, a favorite animated animation

Cartoons. Children who are learning a foreign language may not comprehend the words in the animation, but they will attempt to understand the words they use by seeing how the cartoon characters behave. This approach is intriguing and powerful. Currently, multimedia devices are available in every kindergarten in China. Songs, poetry, stories, and films are used to teach English to young children. It transforms tedious language studies into a fun daily game. Around 10 kids are in each group in Chinese kindergartens, and the teacher frequently employs an instruction strategy depending on the psychology of each child. This calls for the teacher to be not only an educator but also a musician, an artist, a foreign language teacher, and a wonderful mother psychologist. Undoubtedly, the Chinese are providing excellent facilities in this area for the younger generation in the current developing world.

The contribution of facial expressions and gestures to improving education.

By using facial expressions and gestures: when the instructor Through movements and expressions on the face: When the teacher speaks to the students or issues a command, for instance, by utilizing gestures, the students will grasp these words.

The most effective way to teach English is through gesture. Children can quickly locate something's English equivalent in Chinese thanks to Chinese Kindergarten. Animal motions are the simplest way to prepare, as almost every educator is aware. (Monkey) presents himself with his head bent slightly. This will be quite intriguing for kids that have a natural imitative quality and prompt them to speak the name of the animal represented right away. This will motivate you to retain the vocabulary you just learnt. In China, one-child households are the most prevalent. Children from single-parent families thus have a more masculine personality. We should now talk about the teacher. Finding a route to a child's heart with such a persona will not be simple. Children will develop a special affection for a special teacher if they see their teacher as having a kind eye and a nice smile. Children can act autonomously and learn a foreign language in an engaging way with the gesture approach. By doing this, we foster an engaging environment for learning a foreign language.

Conclusion

Here, we will provide a summary of our subject and some suggestions. For instance, In China, the field of education makes extensive use of new mass multimedia techniques. Today, kindergartens effectively integrate the Internet and multimedia technology as teaching instruments to teach young children new abilities. Currently, we should males The most crucial issue at hand is the creation of a new multimedia technology program in Uzbekistan's kindergartens. Preschool education is mostly based on digital technology, thus it is essential to raise and teach children from an early age on the principles of excellent education. The use of modern mass media technologies in Uzbek kindergartens will have a significant impact on the next generation's ability to learn other languages.

-It's possible to argue that childhood is the ideal period for thinking skill development. As a result, preschool educators should base their use of science on the needs (or interests) of the kids. With the aid of modern multimedia technology, it is vital to practice mental development and thinking skills in order to build the capacity to hear, identify colors, and select shapes. It Enhancing children's capacity to take in outside information and promoting the development of complex thought are both crucial.

- Preschool-aged children frequently exhibit lameness in their ability to hear in a foreign language, which indicates that they are not receiving adequate listening instruction. We can see our kids calmly viewing a cartoon under the TV in real life. The moment has come to equip kindergartens with cutting-edge technology today. Continuous exposure to foreign language cartoon lessons is required; if a child learns a second language starting in kindergarten, he will be better able to absorb all information at a later time.

- At the kindergarten age, language abilities are mostly developed by repeated exposure to language. As a result, we can see the changes in children's behavior while we watch a cartoon. Consequently, we can use the cartoon as a useful educational tool

that enhances children's educational effectiveness. Today, some parents are particularly concerned about their kids' interest in cartoons, but in reality, young kids' fantasy plays a major role in how their worldview develops.

Therefore, in education, we can utilize the American equivalent of a remote control, i.e., cartoons, to affect children's language development. We all know that young children gain their thinking and language abilities from real-life experiences at this level, but communication with cartoons at this stage can widen their horizons. In actuality, it is preferable to begin studying a foreign language at a young age. Young children can process new information more faster than adults whose brain activity is completely established since their brain activity is still developing nonstop. It is appropriate to construct a lesson with these characteristics in mind. For instance, teaching a foreign language to preschool-aged children is successful when using games, visuals, songs, and poems.

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